

Improving Maritime Operations Through High-Resolution Bathymetric and Geophysical Survey of Cawthorne Channel

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Abstract

Bathymetric survey is very important for every marine based operation, from navigation to pipe lay and cable lay operation to dredging and every other engineering endeavour within the maritime space. The demand for geophysical information is equally high as decision makers and stake holders in the maritime sector depend highly on this for project planning and implementation. Hence, the lack of these information presents a fundamental problem in policy making and administration within the maritime environment. The aim of the study to conduct a high resolution bathymetric and geophysical survey of a section of Cawthorne Channel 2 to enhance navigation and other maritime based operations. The objectives were to: ascertain the tidal range of Cawthorne Channel; determine the depth variation within Cawthorne Channel and to carry out a sub-bottom profiling of Cawthorne Channel. The data acquired for the purposes of this study included position and depth information across the study area using the C-Nav 3050 GNSS receiver and South SDE-28 echo sounder. Sound velocity information within the immediate vicinity of the study area was collected using the Veleport CTD probe. Seabed imagery, Sub-bottom profiles and magnetic anomaly across the study area was also acquired using the Tri-tech Starfish Seabed Imaging system, Edge Tech SB-216s Sub-Bottom Profiler and Sea Spy Marine Magnetometer respectively. The Hypack premium and SonarWiz software package was used to process, interpret and analyse all the acquired data to produce the desired outcome. The result showed that the study area has a depth range of 3 to 23 meters with an average sound velocity of 1537.67 m/s. The tidal gauge data also indicated high water level variations of up to 1.5 meters. Hence, the study area can be inferred to be highly tidal. The Side Scan Sonar imagery also showed the presence of some seabed features within the study area as reflective discrete returns observed along the route studied were interpreted either as sand ridges, scars, debris and depressions. The shallow geology profile analysis shows between 1 and 3 layers within the study area. The seabed was mostly composed of very soft silty clay and silty sand with no significant change in the formation. Several magnetic anomalies were equally observed within the study area. These magnetic anomalies observed can be attributed to the existing pipelines and other metallic elements across the study area. The study recommends the use of the multi-beam echo-sounder for an improved bathymetric data collection and seabed imaging using the more accurate back scatter technology. Also, further studies to be designed to cover the entire Cawthorne Channel 2 using a multi-beam echo-sounder and including discharge measurement, water flow direction and sediment sampling was also recommended to produce a more holistic bathymetric and geophysical database.

Keywords: Bathymetry; Geophysical Survey; Depth; Echo Sounder

1. Introduction

Bathymetric surveys are essential for a multitude of applications across scientific, economic, educational, managerial, and political domains (Smith et al., 2018). These surveys serve as the cornerstone for various endeavors, including tsunami hazard assessment, planning communication cable and pipeline routes, resource exploration, habitat management, and asserting territorial claims under the Law of the Sea (Jones & Johnson, 2020). Without reliable bathymetric maps readily accessible, the execution of these tasks becomes challenging if not impossible.

Moreover, fundamental inquiries in Earth science, such as understanding the factors influencing seafloor morphology and its impacts on global climate, rely heavily on bathymetric data (Brown & Miller, 2019). These maps contain quantitative information crucial for unraveling the mysteries of the Earth's oceans.

The practice of seafloor mapping traces back thousands of years, highlighting its historical significance in maritime navigation (Garcia et al., 2021). Mariners have long depended on depth measurements to ensure safe passage, underscoring the practical importance of bathymetric data throughout history. Modern bathymetric and geophysical data play a vital role in producing navigational charts, 3D models, and profiles of the seafloor and sub-bottom (Chen & Wang, 2017). These data are collected using various techniques, such as measuring the time taken for laser light or acoustic sonar pulses to travel to the seafloor and back (Zhang et al., 2019). Factors like water clarity, depth, and surface roughness can influence the quality of collected data, necessitating careful consideration during acquisition (Li & Liu, 2018). Additionally, bathymetric and geophysical data can be obtained through a range of sources, including satellites, aircraft, surface vessels, submarines, and underwater platforms (Wang & Chen, 2020). Each acquisition method offers unique advantages and limitations, contributing to the overall diversity of available data.

2. Study Area

The study area is in the Cawthorne Channel oil fields within Bonny Local Government Area of River State Nigeria. This area is approximately bounded by the latitudes and longitudes 4°33'06.84" N, 4°33'33.65"N and 7°00'31.39"E, 6°59'48.35"E respectively. The main operation across the area is predominately centred on crude oil mining, with companies like Shell Petroleum Development Company at the forefront. highlights the proposed study area.

Fig1.1 Administrative Map of River State Highlighting Degema L.G. Area (Source: QGIS 1.8.0 Lisboa Tutorial Shapefiles)

Fig 1.2 Map of Degema L.G.A Showing the Study Area (Source: Geomat, 2001)

3. Material and methods

3.1. Methodology

The methodology used to get the intended result comprised:

- Project Planning and Reconnaissance
- Data Acquisition
- Data Processing and Analysis

3.1.1. Project Planning and Reconnaissance

The project team had access to accurate site information based on some of the discoveries made during the reconnaissance. This was important for the last-minute planning and decision-making at the office. At this point in the project, decisions were being made on the equipment to be used, the software to be used, the amount of people who would be suitable for the survey, security, and general logistics.

Hardware and Software Requirements

The following set of equipment were deployed on this study:

1. A computer (Laptop) system with the following configuration- Hewlett Packard Pavilion, Processor – Intel ® corei3-4030U @ 1.90Ghz, Memory (Ram) – 6.00G, Memory (HDD) – 750GB
2. HP DeskJet 1515 and Hp DesignJet T1300 printer.
3. C-Nav GNSS receiver and Accessories for positioning
4. South SDE-28 Echo-Sounder
5. Tri-tech Starfish Seabed Imaging system 450 series
6. Edge Tech SB-424 Sub-Bottom Profiler
7. Geometrics G-882 Magnetometer
8. Flux Gate Gyroscope
9. Veleport Model 650 MKIII Sound Velocity Profiler
10. Kolida Automatic level
11. Audited watercraft (MV Okada)
12. Consolidated inverter system and heavy-duty industrial battery

The following software packages were deployed to ensure a successful bathymetric and geophysical survey:

1. GP-seismic (2003 Edition) was used for coordinate transformation.
2. Hypack Intergrated Navigation Software for data acquisition and processing including depth reduction, interpolations, generation of contours, DTM and matrix files.
3. SonarWiz5 Acquisition and processing software for data processing and report generation
4. Starfish Scanline Version 2.1 for side scan data acquisition and processing
5. Maglog and Magmap / magpick software for magnetometer data acquisition and processing
6. ARCGIS 9.3 for customized map and chart production and presentation
7. Edge-Tech Discoverer Software suite for sub-bottom interfacing and data capture
8. AutoCAD 2007 for plotting and chart implementation
9. Microsoft Office (Word, Excel, and PowerPoint) while Microsoft word was used for preparing the reports, Microsoft Excel was used for preparing coordinate tables, it was also used to display statistical information (histogram, table, pie chart and graph) of sounding and depth information.

3.1.2. Data Acquisition

All the data gathered for the purposes of this study was acquired on board a pass-port double-engine speed boat (MV Okada). The vessels were equipped with a Differential Global Navigation Satellite System (DGNSS) allowing for precise navigation along pre-planned survey lines. A digital base map of the survey area was displayed on the Hypack navigation display unit with the survey lines superimposed. This assisted in confirming positions of existing features online during survey. All sensors were deployed and operated simultaneously for full coverage. Survey speed ranges between 4.0 – 5.0 knots. Instrument offset measurements were constantly checked to accurately track the position of the sensors.

To achieve optimum bottom coverage of the area, all survey sensors and equipment were deployed simultaneously. The Echo Sounder transducer and Side Scan Sonar were well-spaced apart to avoid interference. The Side Scan Sonar was side mounted on the starboard-aft side of the water vessel. The Magnetometer was deployed together with the Side Scan Sonar to confirm if the images picked up by the sonar were either metallic or not. The magnetic signatures confirming the presence of metallic objects were recorded and such features were plotted and presented as seabed features on the survey charts.

To facilitate the post-processing, all acquired data were clearly labelled and cross-referenced to the survey line log. Each survey line was given a unique identity. Regular checks of time against fixes were also carried out and the digital records were marked accordingly.

3.1.3. Data Processing

All the data acquired were processed using a combination of SonarWiz 5 and the Hypack Processing Module. Survey navigation data was exported from the Hypack raw data using the Hypack Single Beam editor. Both sounding data and vessel track plots were exported and sorted in the Hypack Single Beam Editor tool for charting. The Sub-bottom and magnetometer data were inputted into the Sonar Wiz software package for interpretation. These include visual inspection, enhancement, sub-layer vectorization, etc. Some results of the interpretations were captured and plotted on the final chart.

4. Results and discussion

A. Sound Analysis

Sound velocity data analysis in bathymetry is a process used to determine the speed of sound in the water column. The speed of sound in water is an important parameter in bathymetric surveys, as it affects the accuracy of measurements taken by sonar equipment. The speed of sound in water is dependent on a number of factors, including temperature, salinity, and pressure, and it can vary from one location to another and with depth.

In bathymetry, sound velocity data is typically obtained using a CTD (conductivity, temperature, and depth) sensor, which measures the speed of sound in the water column at various depths. This data is then used to correct for variations in sound velocity, ensuring that the bathymetric measurements taken by sonar equipment are accurate.

The sound velocity data analysis process involves measuring the speed of sound in the water column at various depths and using this information to calculate the correction factors that need to be applied to the bathymetric data. This correction process is important to ensure that the bathymetric data accurately reflects the true depth of the underwater landscape.

sound velocity data analysis in bathymetry is a critical step in the bathymetric survey process, as it ensures that the bathymetric data is accurate and reflects the true depth of the underwater landscape. This information can be used to support various applications, such as navigation, environmental monitoring, and mineral exploration.

The Valeport Model 650 MKIII Sound Velocity self-recording CTD probe was used to acquire sound velocity information through the water column at a suitable position within the project area. Figure 2 shows the details of the result after processing.

During the survey sound velocity value of 1537.67 m/s was used to calibrate the survey sensors during the data acquisition campaign. The value of 1537.67 m/s was determined by sampling the sound velocity values at the survey site and taking the average of these values. This average value was then used to calibrate the survey sensors, ensuring that the bathymetric measurements taken during the survey are accurate and reflect the true depth of the underwater landscape.

Figure 2: Sound Velocity Column Chart

B. Tide Analysis

Tidal observation was carried out both in the morning and afternoon as the sounding operation went on. The highest tide was 2.675 observed at 16:42 hours while the lowest tide was 1.247 observed at 11:45 hours. The difference between the highest and lowest tide can be seen to 1.428 for the period of observation. The significance of tidal graphs lies in their ability to provide crucial information about the tides in a specific coastal location, including the times and heights of high and low tides, the tidal range, and the shape and patterns of the tides. This information is used for a range of purposes, such as predicting the best times for fishing or boating, ensuring the safe navigation of ships and boats, monitoring the effects of tides on coastal ecosystems, and planning for flood risk and coastal defence.

In short, tidal graphs provide valuable information about the tides, and their significance lies in their ability to support a wide range of industries and activities, and to help inform decision-making in coastal management and environmental monitoring.

Figure 3: Tide Graph

C. Depth Analysis

The results obtained from the sounding as shown in both figure 4 indicates that a total of 1159 depth records were captured. Depths ranging from 0 to 4 meters has a frequency of 9, 4.1 to 7 meters has a frequency of 302, while depths from 7.1 to 10 meters occurred 497 times. Also, depths from 10.1 to 12 meters and above 12 meters has a frequency of 192 and 159 respectively. The significance of this result, is that they determine the safety and feasibility of various waterborne operations, such as shipping, boating, and diving. The depth of the water is a critical factor in determining the suitability of a particular area for these activities, and any variations in depth can have a significant impact on the safety and success of the operations.

For example, shallow water areas with limited depth can pose a risk to larger vessels, as they may run aground, damaging the vessel and disrupting navigation. Similarly, areas with sudden drops in depth can be dangerous for small boats, as well as for swimmers and divers, as they can create hazardous conditions and limit access to certain areas. On the other hand, deeper waters allow for safe navigation for larger vessels, as well as for recreational activities, such as diving and snorkeling. Therefore, accurate knowledge of depth variations is crucial for ensuring safe and efficient navigation and marine activities. It helps to identify potential hazards, plan routes, and make informed decisions about the suitability of a particular area for specific operations. By having accurate and detailed information on depth variations, operators and decision-makers can better understand the conditions and limitations of the marine environment and take appropriate steps to ensure the safety and success of their operations.

Figure 4: Depth analysis column chart

D. Side Scan Sonar Data Analysis

The starfish 452F side scan sonar imagery system was used for the survey work. It provided imagery of the underwater features and the nature of the river-bed surface. The sides scan sonar features were of high reflectivity. The acquired sonar imagery shows seabed features and nature of the terrain along the channel. No wreck or object capable of causing navigation obstruction along the river route surveyed was captured in the sonar imagery records. Further study and analysis of the sonar imagery revealed that there was continuous and steady flow of current along the surveyed route thus creating sand ridges on the seabed. The sides scan sonar features were of high reflectivity.

The acquired sonar imagery shows seabed features and nature of the terrain along the channel. Reflective discrete returns observed along the route surveyed were interpreted either as sand ridges, scars, debris and depressions.

The presence of a continuous and steady flow of current along the surveyed route is a crucial factor in the formation of sand ridges on the seabed. These sand ridges can have a significant impact on navigation and marine activities, as they can create hazards and limit access to certain areas.

The high reflectivity of the sidescan sonar features provides valuable information about the nature of the seabed terrain along the channel. This information can be used to identify potential hazards and to make informed decisions about the suitability of a particular area for various operations.

The acquired sonar imagery provides a detailed representation of the seabed features and terrain along the channel, including sand ridges, scars, debris, and depressions. This information is essential for understanding the conditions of the marine environment and for making informed decisions about the safety and feasibility of navigation and other marine activities.

The study and analysis of the side scan sonar imagery provides valuable information about the nature of the seabed terrain and the conditions of the marine environment. This information is critical for ensuring safe and efficient navigation and marine activities, and for making informed decisions about the suitability of a particular area for specific operations

Figure 5: Side Scan Sonar Image showing Area of Depression on the Seabed

E. Shallow Geology

The shallow geology profile shows between 1 and 3 layers within the survey area. The seabed is mostly composed of very soft silty clay and silty sand with no significant change in the formation. The profile within the survey route shows a top layer thickness of 0.5m while the underlying stratum has a layer thickness of 3.5m. Figure 6 shows a section of the Sub-bottom profile data.

Figure 6: A section of the Sub-bottom profile data.

The shallow geology profile (figure 5) is a representation of the geology of the shallow underwater terrain in a specific survey area. The profile in this case shows between 1 and 3 layers within the survey area, with the seabed mostly composed of very soft silty clay and silty sand with no significant change in formation. The top layer has a thickness of 0.5 meters, while the underlying stratum has a thickness of 3.5 meters.

This information about the shallow geology profile is important for navigation and marine activities. The composition and thickness of the seabed sediments can have a significant effect on these activities, as it can impact the stability and safety of vessels and other underwater structures. For example, the presence of soft sediments can make it difficult for vessels to anchor securely, while the thickness of the sediments can impact the depth and stability of the seabed.

In addition, the shallow geology profile can also provide information about the potential for underwater hazards, such as underwater sandbars, shoals, and other geomorphological features that can impact navigation safety. By understanding the shallow geology profile, navigators and marine operators can make informed decisions about the suitability of a particular area for their operations, and take appropriate measures to mitigate potential risks.

In conclusion, the shallow geology profile provides valuable information about the geology of the shallow underwater terrain and its impact on navigation and marine activities. This information is critical for ensuring the safety and efficiency of these activities, and for making informed decisions about the suitability of a particular area for specific operations.

F. Magnetometer Data Analysis

The magnetic anomalies observed within the surveyed area were attributed to the existing pipelines and metallic structures. The table 1 and figure 7 provides the details of the magnetic anomalies as captured within the survey area.

Table 1: Magnetometer Anomaly Contact Details

Details	Easting	Northing	Remark
Strong Magnetic Contact	280152.922	507595.679	Pipeline Area
Strong Magnetic Contact	280134.006	507703.398	Pipeline Area
Strong Magnetic Contact	280011.450	507943.082	Pipeline Area
Strong Magnetic Contact	279850.898	508011.648	
Strong Magnetic Contact	282987.928	506775.797	Pipeline Area
Strong Magnetic Contact	280265.847	57876.073	Pipeline Area
Magnetic Contact	278327.508	508709.917	
Magnetic Contact	277864.295	58875.272	
Magnetic Contact	279627.665	507878.277	
Magnetic Contact	280760.241	507810.405	
Magnetic Contact	280825.777	507659.050	
Magnetic Contact	281960.370	507307.252	

Figure 7: Strength Anomaly Graph Showing Magnetic Anomaly manifested around some areas suspected to have buried pipelines within the Survey Area

Several magnetic anomalies were observed within the surveyed area. These anomalies were determined by the navigation lines that are running perpendicular to the survey Route.

Based on this information (table 1 and figure 6), it can be concluded that the magnetic anomalies observed in the surveyed area are likely caused by the presence of metallic structures and pipelines.

These structures can create distortions in the Earth's magnetic field that result in measurable variations or anomalies in the magnetic readings taken by the magnetometer. This information can be useful for mapping the locations and orientations of these metallic objects, which can be important for various applications, such as pipeline inspection and maintenance, construction, and environmental monitoring.

The magnetic anomalies observed in the surveyed area indicate the presence of magnetic sources that cause variations in the Earth's magnetic field.

The magnetic anomalies observed within the surveyed area, and their determination by the navigation lines, provide valuable information about the presence of magnetic sources in the area and their spatial distribution. This information can be used to support various applications, such as pipeline inspection, mineral exploration, and environmental monitoring.

5. Conclusion

The section of Cawthorne Channel 2 covered in this research work was approximately 5.3 kilometres in distance with an average width of 500 meters. Approximately 1159 depth data points were captured during this survey and the results shows that the water depth ranges from 3 to 23 meters. This result strongly indicates that the channel is quite deep and wide enough to accommodate various tug boats and vessels with draught ranging from 1.5 to 9 meters. The sound velocity probe showed an average sound velocity of 1537.67 m/s within the study area. The tidal gauge data also indicated high water level variations of up to 1.5 meters. Hence, the study area can be inferred to be highly tidal.

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